

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL STUDY OF THE CURE-INDUCED DEFORMATIONS IN COMPOSITES PRODUCED BY VACUUM INFUSION

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1 Introduction

When curing thermoset-based composite materials, the resin transforms from the liquid state to the solid state which induces deformations due to the thermal expansion and chemical shrinkage phenomena. The contact conditions with the mould as well as the atmospheric pressure exerted on the part prevent these deformations from developing freely so that internal stresses build up. Upon demoulding, a part of the internal stresses is released resulting in the appearance of distortions and some residual stresses remain in the material. Distortion of the part will depend on several factors such as, among others, the geometry, the materials used, the stacking sequences, the temperature history seen at each point in the part as a result of the cure cycle being applied or the contact conditions with the mould [1, 2]. The main challenges behind an accurate prediction of the residual stresses and deformations are the use of a model complexity level suited to the problem being studied, the material parameter values put into the model and the computing power required.

The present study aims at studying experimentally some of the effects affecting the cure-induced deformations and at trying to model these properly. Angle brackets with different features are considered to study factors affecting spring-in angle. The spring-in angle $\Delta\theta$ characterizes the difference between the nominal geometry or mould geometry and the cured geometry for angle brackets as illustrated on Figure 1.

2. Experimental

After cure, parts generally undergo different steps such as demoulding, removing the peel-ply, post-curing... All these steps can cause additional stresses in the material and influence the deformations. The influence of these steps as well as cure temperature, number of plies and post-cure on spring-in angle has

been studied experimentally. The parameters are listed in Table 1.

The angle brackets were made using an epoxy resin male mould. The mould angle has been measured to 89.99°, with a fillet radius of 5.64 mm. No female mould was used so the fibres were maintained only by the vacuum bag. The angle brackets are 280 mm long with 100 mm long flanges. The parts are produced by vacuum infusion with a Saertex quasi UD glass fabrics (90% of the fibres in the warp direction) and the Araldite LY5052/Hardener HY5052 epoxy resin system produced by Huntsman. The stacking sequence is the same for all the parts: the fibres are oriented in the direction perpendicular to the y-axis on Figure 2, which is the 0° direction.

The heating of the parts and mould were done as follows: the mould was preheated at the target cure temperature and the resin was then infused in the oven with the resin at room temperature. The parts were cured long enough to reach their maximal degree of cure and then cooled to room temperature. The mould temperature was recorded using a thermocouple during the following phases: fibres drying, resin infusion, curing and post-curing. Some specimens were post-cured freestanding in an oven at 100°C during an hour, and a one centimetre wide strip was then milled on each edge of the plate.

The distortions are measured using a Nikon MMDx50 laser scanner mounted on a 7-axis Metrology-grade MCA II arm. The declared accuracy is 50 µm which leads to an incertitude of 0.1° on the spring-in angle measured. Laser measurements were taken on the parts after various stages of the manufacturing process: before and after the removal of the peel ply, after milling, right after and one week after post-cure. The influence of the cure temperature, the post-cure and the number of plies on the spring-in angle was studied using the

design of experiment presented in Table 2: each factor is studied separately from the others. Each configuration was manufactured at least 5 times in order to smooth the differences between experimental conditions.

To measure the spring-in angle distribution, the scans were split evenly along the angle bracket in different sections. For each section, one line is fitted on each flange (see Figure 2) and the spring-in is computed from these two direction vectors. The spring-in angle is defined as the difference between the part angle before cure (mould angle) and the measured angle after cure as illustrated on Figure 1. To obtain the final value of the spring-in, the values calculated for each section of each experiment were averaged.

3. Results and discussion

A typical spring-in distribution result for an angle bracket is shown on Figure 3, at every manufacturing step where the angle was measured. It appears that removing the peel-ply (red curve) doesn't have any significant effect and doesn't influence the distortions. Indeed, the difference between before and after the removal of the peel-ply remains within the 0.1° incertitude of the measure, except on the right edge, which is interpreted as an edge effect. However, the post-cure (green curve) has a significant effect on spring-in angle.

Table 3 presents the experimental results of the effect of number of plies, cure temperature and post-cure on spring-in angle, with the standard deviation, for each configuration. The drop-off in spring-in observed between 6- and 12-ply parts and the increase in spring-in between the parts cured at 50°C and 70°C are in good agreement with the results obtained in other study [1, 3]. Attention should be paid while interpreting the spring-in value for the "6 plies, 50°C" case because of the important standard deviation observed ($\pm 3.71E-1$).

4. Numerical simulation

The numerical prediction methodology that is used consists in performing coupled chemical-thermal-mechanical finite elements calculations using FE package ABAQUS with the help of user material subroutines. The details of the model follow the approach suggested by Svanberg and Holmberg [4] which considers a simplified linear viscoelastic behaviour of the material where time-temperature-degree of cure superposition is applied. Three of the

main assumptions made are: (i) the stresses and strains are assumed to be zero until gelation, (ii) both thermal expansion and chemical shrinkage are assumed to be linear within each material state, and, (iii) the shift factor is approximated as a step function, so that the material properties are kept constant for each relevant state, rubbery or glassy, of the resin as illustrated on Figure 4. The material properties used for numerical simulations are those used in [5]. The transition from the rubbery to glassy state happens when the resin temperature reaches its glass transition temperature T_g which is assumed to depend only on the degree of cure X . The model used to predict the glass transition temperature T_g as a function of the degree of cure X is the one used in [6] and reminded in the following equations:

$$T_g = 128 - 250(1 - X) \quad [^\circ\text{C}] \quad (1)$$

where the degree of cure X is computed from the kinetic law:

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = 110000e^{\left(-\frac{52600}{R(T+273.15)}\right)}X^{0.17}(X_{max} - X)^{0.83} \quad (2)$$

$$X_{max} = 0.782 + 0.002T \quad (3)$$

where X , R and T are the degree of cure, the gas constant and the cure temperature in Celsius degrees, respectively.

Even with the assumptions made, 30 material properties are needed in total for both states, rubbery and glassy.

The boundary condition applied is a freestanding-cure which means that the part is free to deform. The rigid body motions are blocked to prevent the part to move. This is a strong approximation comparing to the experimental setup since the pressure applied on top on the part by the vacuum bag keep it against the mould. Furthermore, the mould prevents the angle to close. These behaviours are not reflected by the boundary condition applied, but this simplified approach has shown good agreement with experimental data in [5].

The angle brackets modeled are similar to the one experimentally manufactured: 6 and 12 plies and two different cure cycles regarding the cure temperature and post-cure. As no warpage behaviour would result from the simulation, only a 1 mm large bracket was modeled. Indeed, no effect in the length

direction is expected since all the plies have the same orientation, the part thickness is constant, mechanical properties are uniform in the part and no temperature gradient is applied in the length direction (y direction on Figure 2).

A mesh convergence study has been run in order to get the best accuracy/computational cost ratio. The angle brackets were modelled using three dimensional brick element with 20 nodes (C3D20). The different meshes studied are detailed in Table 4. Since a global size was imposed, refining the size of the elements in the y-direction lead to refine the mesh in the 0° direction. The results of the mesh convergence study presented on Figures 5 and 6 in term of spring-in and computational time cost respectively. The relative difference in term of spring-in between the results obtained on the finest mesh (number 8) and the coarser one is about 4%. Regarding this small difference and the computation time, it was therefore decided to use the mesh number 2 in the following simulations.

The post-processing consists in extracting the angles before and after post-curing step in order to compute the spring-in.

6. Comparison

The spring-in values obtained by numerical simulations for the different configurations are presented in Table 5. These numerical results are compared to the experimental ones on Figures 7 and 8 in order to highlight the influence of the different parameters tested on the spring-in angle:

- Cure temperature

The simulation performed in this study is able to predict the behaviour observed experimentally and are in agreement with other studies [3]: a higher cure temperature increases the spring-in angle since both thermal strains and degree of cure are more important when the cure temperature is higher.

- Post-cure

Numerical simulations can predict the effect observed experimentally of the post-cure on the spring-in angle: the post-cure tends to increase the spring-in angle. Svanberg and al. explained this phenomenon by the frozen-in deformations that appear in the parts constrained by the vacuum bag [3]. During post cure these strains are released when

the material transforms for the first time from the glassy to rubbery state. Releasing these strains results in increasing the spring-in angle. If the frozen-in strains are higher at higher cure temperature, releasing these strains results in an increase of the spring-in angle when the cure temperature is higher.

- Number of plies

The simulation results are not significantly influenced by the thickness of the parts while experimental results showed a reduction of the spring-in angle for thicker parts. Experimental results are in accordance with observations made in other studies and reported in [1, 7, 8]. Radfort and Rennick in [7] and Darrow and Smith in [8] have shown the link between the part thickness and the spring-in evolution: the higher thermal expansion coefficient of the tool compared to the expansion coefficient of the part induces residual stresses at the tool-part interface. These stresses act on a certain depth of influence which becomes less significant regarding the part thickness when increasing the thickness of the laminate. Wisnom and al. showed in [9] that the tool part interaction is not the only factors that links the influence of the part thickness on the spring-in angle by curing parts on a tool made of the same material as the parts in order to get rid of the thermal mismatch: it has been shown on C-shaped geometry that decreasing the arc length/part thickness ratio reduces the spring-in angle due to shearing that can occur [9]. Regarding the spring-in angle values, it can be seen that the numerical simulation tends to overestimate the values (except for the “6 plies, 50°C + pc” case). For the 6 plies parts, the spring-in values predicted are close to the measured ones: the difference doesn't exceed 0.1°.

Since most of the material properties used were not measured experimentally on the actual material being considered but taken instead from the literature on woven fabric [5], a sensitivity analysis was carried out to assess the impact of the properties uncertainty on the distortion results and, hence, identify the particular material properties that need to be characterized more precisely to improve the accuracy of the simulation. The analysis was conducted using the in-house software Minamo, which allows performing a sample-based sensitivity, in which the simulation was done repeatedly with different sets of input parameters chosen randomly.

Variations of +/- 10% in the parameters around the initial values were allowed. The result of this analysis is presented on Figure 9. The transverse coefficient of thermal expansion in the transverse direction at the glassy state has the major influence and should be determined accurately in order to improve the simulation results by reducing the uncertainty on the values.

7. Conclusion

The comparison between experimental and simulation results have helped evaluating the cure model developed by Svanberg and al. in [4] and implemented at Cenaero. Regarding experimental results and previous observations, the model is able to predict the effect of the cure temperature and post-cure on the cure-induced spring-in. Experimental results showed that if the post-cure step has a significant effect on the spring-in angle, the removal of the peel-ply doesn't influence the deformation. Even if the boundary condition, i.e. freestanding cure, implemented in the present study gave good results regarding the experimental data, other boundary conditions such as a fully-constrained cure followed by a demoulding step or applying a pressure on the top of the part to account for the effect of the vacuum bag, for instance, have to be evaluated in future works to try to be closer to the experimental results. The sensitivity analysis performed showed that the predicted spring-in computed with the model implemented is significantly affected by the transverse coefficient of thermal expansion of the material in the transverse direction at the glassy state. Therefore, experimental TMA measurement, for instance, of this material property seems necessary in order to improve the accuracy of the numerical simulations in future works. Other studies such as [1, 10, 11] have shown the importance of modelling the tool-part interaction in predicting cure-induced deformations. This modelisation hasn't been done in the present study but seems to be a key point in order to improve the accuracy of the numerical simulations of cure-induced deformations.

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	T _c [°C]	Nb of plies	Post-cure
1	50	6	yes
2	70	12	no

Tab. 1. Range of the parameter values considered in the study of the spring-in angle shown by the angle brackets.

Configurations	T _c [°C]	Nb of plies	Post-cure
A	1	1	1
B	1	1	2
C	1	2	1
D	1	2	2
E	2	1	1
F	2	1	2
G	2	2	1
H	2	2	2

Tab. 2. Plan of experiments used to study the influence of the 3 parameters studied on the spring-in angle. Numbers refer to those in Table 1.

Configurations	Measured spring-in	Standard deviation
6 plies, 50°C	5.96E-1	3.71E-1
6 plies, 50°C + pc	7.24E-1	1.64E-1
6 plies, 70°C	7.82E-1	4.48E-2
6 plies, 70°C + pc	8.57E-1	7.23E-2
12 plies, 50°C	4.85E-1	1.04E-1
12 plies, 50°C + pc	4.57E-1	8.67E-2
12 plies, 70°C	6.32E-1	3.77E-2
12 plies, 70°C + pc	6.95E-1	5.50E-2

Tab. 3. Experimental results of the influence of the number of plies, cure temperature and post-cure on spring-in angle. The application of a freestanding post-cure step is written "pc".

N ^o	Nb of elements in the y-direction	Nb of elements in the thickness direction
1	1	2
2	1	4
3	1	8
4	2	4
5	2	8
6	4	8
7	4	12
8	6	8

Tab. 4. Specifications of the meshes used for the mesh convergence study.

Configurations	Predicted spring-in
6 plies, 50°C	6.36E-1
6 plies, 50°C + pc	6.84E-1
6 plies, 70°C	8.78E-1
6 plies, 70°C + pc	9.63E-1
12 plies, 50°C	6.36E-1
12 plies, 50°C + pc	6.85E-1
12 plies, 70°C	8.79E-1
12 plies, 70°C + pc	9.64E-1

Tab. 5. Prediction of the influence of the number of plies, cure temperature and post-cure on spring-in angle. The application of a freestanding post-cure step is written "pc".

Fig. 1. Definition of the spring-in angle.

Fig. 2. Spring-in angle calculation

Fig. 3. Influence of several finishing steps on spring-in angle

Fig. 4. Mechanical properties are kept constant for each relevant state, glassy or rubbery. The green curve represents the real behaviour while the red one is the approximation made.

Fig. 6. Computation time of the FE simulation for each mesh specified in Table 4. The time is given in hh:mm:ss format.

Fig. 5. Predicted spring-in angle for each mesh specified in Table 4.

Fig. 7. Comparison between experimental and predicted results for the 6 plies laminate.

Fig. 8. Comparison between experimental and predicted results for the 12 plies laminate.

Fig. 9. Importance of the material properties determination on the simulation results. Indices r and g stand for glassy and rubbery states respectively.